

POLITICAL SCIENCES

THE INVOLVEMENT OF THE UN SECURITY COUNCIL IN THE SETTLEMENT OF INTERNATIONAL DISPUTES

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ABSTRACT

The establishment of the UN could not eliminate all international conflicts, nor could it guarantee collective security or respect for the principle of non-use of force. However, the organization contributes to the fulfillment of these goals through cooperation between member states and the involvement of its bodies in resolving disputes.

The Security Council has the main responsibility for maintaining international peace and security, being the only body that analyzes the appropriateness of its intervention and establishes the methods of action in the event of a conflict, methods that can be considered incompatible with the reality of the current environment of international relations.

Keywords: United Nations, Security Council, veto, conflict, right to self-defense, security.

Introduction

The League of Nations Convention, signed in 1924, indirectly mentions the existence of international organizations in Article 23, which suggests the creation of specialized international organizations to promote international cooperation.¹

The worldwide recognition of this organization can be deduced from the preamble to the Charter of the United Nations, which states that *"The Governments have established an international organization to be known as the United Nations"*.

The United Nations has as its main purpose the maintenance of international peace and security, the promotion of economic, social and cultural cooperation and respect for human rights. No other international organization has a competence as broad as that of the UN. This is clear from Article 55 of the Charter, which gives the UN the right to authorize action by Member States in these fields, in cooperation with its institutions.

However, its powers are limited in terms of its ability to intervene in "matters which are essentially within the domestic jurisdiction of a State", according to Article 2(7) of the Charter, except those relating to international peace and security, in particular the powers of the Security Council in matters of dispute or international situations submitted to it for its consideration.

The United Nations system is considered to have a threefold competence: to draft documents regulating human rights and fundamental freedoms, to establish ways to promote and respect the legal norms in this area, and to take action in cases of gross violations of human rights.² To this end, specific mechanisms have been set up, bodies whose main purpose is to fulfill the purposes for which the UN was established.

Thus, the *UN Security Council* is the body with a political and decision-making role in all important matters concerning the Organization and has the main competence in the maintenance of international peace and security. Its general objective is set out in Article 24 of the UN Charter, according to which it acts on behalf of all UN Member States.

Security Council's role in resolving international conflicts

The exercise of its powers is based on the provisions of Chapter VI (Peaceful Settlement of Disputes), Chapter VII (Action in case of threats to the peace, breaches of the peace and acts of aggression) and Chapter VIII of the UN Charter (Regional Agreements).

In order to fulfill its *conflict prevention* mandate, the Security Council has been involved in the situation in Kosovo with regard to the determination of its legal status. To this end, the UN deployed the UNMIK mission, initiated in 1999 by Security Council Resolution 1244³, following the outbreak of conflict between the Kosovo region and Serbia. The main demands of the Security Council based on this resolution were the cessation of hostilities, the withdrawal of military troops from Kosovo, the provision of security in the area so that refugees could return to their territory, and the cooperation of neighboring states to protect and promote human rights.

According to this resolution, the President of Serbia called on the Security Council to intervene to prevent the adoption of a unilateral declaration of independence of the area, in order to respect the territorial integrity of the country, the provisions of international law, the UN Charter and Resolution 1244.

Following Kosovo's self-proclamation of independence in 2008, the Council was unable to reach any agreement on the status of the region, with Russia being one of the permanent members with a strong interest in

¹The Covenant of the League of Nations, 1924, text available online at https://avalon.law.yale.edu/20th_century/leagcov.asp, art.23, accessed 19.02.2025.

²Cloșcă I., Suceavă I., Human Rights Treatise, Europa Nova Publishing House, Bucharest 1995, p. 406.

³United Nations Resolution S/RES/1244 (1999), text available at <https://unmik.unmissions.org/united-nations-resolution-1244>, accessed 19.02.2025.

the conflict zone. The only decision taken by the Council in this case was to continue the UNMIK mission to monitor the territory in order to avoid a resumption of violence, which prompted Serbia to ask the General Assembly to refer the matter to the International Court of Justice for an advisory opinion on the legality of Kosovo's unilateral declaration of independence.

In this regard, the Court issued an advisory opinion stating that Kosovo's declaration of independence did not violate international law⁴, without expressly stipulating that it was lawful, precisely in order not to create a precedent on the basis of which other territories would try to proclaim independence, in which context the opinion was limited to the situation of Kosovo.

The Security Council also fulfils a *peacekeeping function*, under which it has the power to call a ceasefire and send UN forces into conflict territory, but only with the consent of the states involved.⁵

The Council also fulfills *peace-making functions* by helping to settle disputes before they escalate into conflicts involving the use of armed force. To this end, it has the right to invite the parties to settle their dispute by one of the peaceful means provided for in Article 33(2). (1), i.e. negotiations, inquiries, conciliation, arbitration, judicial proceedings, recourse to regional organizations or arrangements, and, under Article 38 of the Charter, it may make recommendations at the request of all parties to the dispute with a view to its amicable settlement.

Although the Council's powers are recognized worldwide to deal with international security issues, they are limited by political disagreements between the permanent members caused by the abuse of the veto and the way the right to individual and collective self-defense is interpreted.

The limits of the Council's powers in relation to the invocation of the right to individual and collective self-defense

Article 51 of the Charter allows any UN member state to react immediately in the event of an attack against it, on the basis of the right of self-defense, without waiting for a decision by the Security Council.

Thus, the State's freedom to act is limited by its obligation to inform the Council of the measures it has adopted, which shall not affect the right of the Council to take any other action it deems necessary for the maintenance of international peace and security.

Article 51 must be interpreted in conjunction with Art. 2 para. (4) of the Charter, which prohibits both the use of force and the threat of force in international relations.

The use of force can only be accepted internationally against those who have violated fundamental international values, for the protection of all members of the

community, and the right of self-defense cannot be exercised in an arbitrary or abusive manner.

According to Art. 39 of the Charter, the Council has the power to determine whether or not there is an attack or threat to international security, but it must not extend this right without limit by categorizing a crisis situation existing on the territory of a state as a threat to international peace.

The concept of the 'right of individual or collective self-defense' needs to be defined in much clearer terms in terms of when a state can act pre-emptively to protect itself against a violation of its sovereignty as a result of an imminent or perceived armed attack, given that some states have exercised this right in advance, such as the US military intervention in Afghanistan and Iraq.

In order to avoid this legislative gap in the future, an express provision should be introduced in the Charter determining whether the right of self-defense can be invoked on the basis of an anticipated attack before the aggressor State has actually carried out the act of aggression.

The right to self-defense was also invoked in Nicaragua's case against the United States at the International Court of Justice in The Hague in 1986. During the trial, the conditions for the exercise of this right were analyzed and it was considered that, in order to be invoked, it is necessary to take into account the necessity and proportionality of the attack, the anticipated attack in self-defense of a State being justified only if there is an imminent threat of attack by another State against that State.⁶

The distinction between a pre-emptive and a pre-emptive attack should be expressly stipulated in the Charter so that States can no longer abuse the right of self-defense. An attack can therefore be considered to be pre-emptive if there is evidence of a plan containing specific acts of aggression by another State, whereas a pre-emptive attack is an attack against a potential, abstract danger for which there is no concrete evidence of preparation of an attack and can be categorized as unlawful.⁷

The veto in the current security environment

The Security Council has the right to commit UN forces and take direct action against threats to international peace and security. In the decision-making process, the permanent members are vested with a veto, which can block the adoption of certain decisions. As far as the adoption of decisions is concerned, it cannot be subject to any external control by the General Assembly or the International Court of Justice.

The structure of the Council and the conditions under which voting rights can be exercised were laid down at the Yalta Conference. The origin of the veto and the reasons for its establishment were determined

⁴ICJ Report, Accordance with international law of the unilateral declaration of independence in respect of Kosovo, advisory opinion of July 22, 2010, text available at <https://www.icj-cij.org/public/files/case-related/141/141-20100722-ADV-01-00-EN.pdf>, accessed on 19.02.2025.

⁵Lungu M.D., *The Role of International Organizations in the Peaceful Settlement of International Disputes*, Universul Juridic Publishing House, Bucharest, 2010, p.213.

⁶Case concerning military and paramilitary activities in and against Nicaragua, June 27, 1986, ICJ Reports 1986, para. 176, pp. 94-95, text available at <https://www.icj-cij.org/public/files/case-related/70/070-19860627-JUD-01-00-EN.pdf>, accessed on 21.02.2025.

⁷Lascu A.L., *Crima de agresiune-Un updating sau un upgrading necesar*, Revista Universul Juridic nr. 2, February 2016, p. 129.

by the political interests of the three victors of the Second World War, the United States, Great Britain and the Soviet Union.

Great Britain sought to maintain its influence in the colonies, the USA wanted to ensure that the USSR would get involved in the war in the Pacific, while the Soviet Union had an interest in consolidating its position in conquered territories, especially Poland, and in expanding its sphere of influence in Asia.

Also, the main condition for Russia's acceptance of UN membership was that the permanent members, later including France and China, would acquire veto power so that the five could have extensive control over the world. The decisions taken at Yalta were widely criticized on the grounds that Roosevelt had left eastern Europe and northeast Asia under the political influence of the USSR, which was seen as an act of treason.⁸

The introduction of the veto right in the UN Charter created inequality between states, as it allowed permanent members to block the adoption of any resolutions, including those that could affect them, thus placing them above the provisions of the Charter by giving them immunity from measures that could be adopted against them.

Inequality is also manifested in the limited capacity of states to support military operations authorized by the Council, as well as in their financial contributions, which have made permanent members the Organization's main donors.

The way in which UN members are elected is another form of inequality, as the General Assembly has to decide by a two-thirds majority whether a state is admitted, after having obtained the proposal of the Security Council, i.e. without any of the permanent members having vetoed it. The General Assembly will therefore not be able to decide without the recommendation of the Security Council.⁹

If these conditions were strictly complied with, they could allow for the exclusion of certain members that do not comply with the provisions of the Charter, according to Art. 6. However, no permanent member will ever agree to such a measure being taken against them. If the acceptance of some states as UN members has been delayed for some time, this has been for reasons of political interests unrelated to the conditions of membership stipulated in the Charter, and no member has ever been excluded, although there are states whose actions are denounced by the UN, but also by other international organizations, as is the case with Russia following the outbreak of the conflict in Ukraine.

Given that some of the permanent members represent some of the world's major economic powers, their decisions influence the settlement of disputes. In this sense, although UN member states that are not permanent members cannot exercise their veto, they can be

considered to have a global political and economic influence that could qualify them as Council members, such as Germany or Japan, which represent some of the largest contributors to the UN budget. Brazil and India are also among the top troop contributors under the UN peace mandate.

Although the financial contributions of some states have increased in recent years, they have limited military capability, which makes it less likely that they will be able to participate in missions involving the use of armed force.

Regarding the reform of the Security Council, the 2005 UN Summit Outcome document¹⁰ envisaged the need for a new Council structure characterized by a broad representation of its members, but it does not contain any explicit specification or time frame for the expansion of the Security Council, as no compromise was reached on this issue.

The large number of member states in the General Assembly, their inability to contribute financially to the UN budget and their inability to contribute troops to UN operations are factors that hamper the Council's reform process.

One of the proposals aims to bring the G4 group of Brazil, Germany, India and Japan into the Council as permanent members and to expand it with six permanent members, two from Africa, two from Asia, one from Latin America and one from the Western European Group, as well as four new elected members (one each from Africa, Asia, Latin America and the Eastern European Group).¹¹ However, this proposal failed to secure a two-thirds majority of UN member states' votes to adopt the resolution, and the existence of permanent members makes it impossible to revise the Charter.

Subsequently, various proposals have been made to try to reform the Security Council, but without reaching a compromise, and the subject will be debated further in General Assembly meetings.

Although the veto has many disadvantages, it can also be seen as an advantage in that it prevents any of the permanent members from gaining the support of a sufficient number of Council members to violate the Charter, since its decisions are adopted by a vote of nine members, according to Article 27 of the Charter.

The right of veto thus makes it possible to block the adoption of a decision contrary to the law, and is a means for the Council to control itself in order to avoid any direct military confrontation between the permanent members.¹²

Russia's war in Ukraine in 2022 has once again raised the question of giving up the veto and reforming the UN Security Council. However, sanctioning Russia by excluding it from the Council is a complicated procedure, beset by a number of legislative inconsistencies

⁸Office of the Historian, The Yalta Conference, 1945, text available at <https://history.state.gov/milestones/1937-1945/yalta-conf>, accessed 21.02.2025.

⁹UN Charter, Art. 4, text available at <https://legislatie.just.ro/Public/DetaliiDocumentAfis/19362>, accessed on 22.02.2025.

¹⁰Resolution adopted by the General Assembly A/RES/60/1/2005, p. 153, available at

https://www.un.org/en/development/desa/population/migration/generalassembly/docs/globalcompact/A_RES_60_1.pdf, accessed on 22.02.2025.

¹¹UN Security Council Reform, text available at <https://www.mae.ro/node/1589>, accessed on 23.02.2025.

¹²Sur. S., International Relations, 7th revised edition, C.H.Beck Publishing House, Bucharest, 2021, p.435.

and the political interests of the other permanent members, mainly the US.

Although it violates a sovereign state's rights to self-determination and territorial integrity, Russia wants to keep Ukraine within its sphere of influence mainly to prevent Ukraine from joining NATO or deepening relations with the EU.

Russia's exclusion from the Security Council is a sanction allowed by the UN Charter under Article 6, but it is a difficult desideratum to achieve, given that Council decisions must be approved by at least nine members, but can be rejected if only one of the permanent members exercises its veto. In this case, it is impossible for Russia to vote against its own interests.

By way of exception, in the event of possible removal from the Council, Russia would retain its status in the General Assembly, and the exclusion of members from the General Assembly can be decided by a two-thirds majority of the members present and voting, according to Art. 18 para. (2) of the Charter, a situation which is hardly conceivable in practice, given the diversity of States in the Assembly and the impossibility of achieving unanimity in this respect, determined by conflicting political interests.

If an attempt were to be made to revise the Charter to remove Russia from the Council, the process would be blocked by the refusal of the permanent members to ratify the amendments, since according to Article 108, amendments enter into force if adopted by a two-thirds majority of the members of the General Assembly and ratified by two-thirds of the Members of the United Nations, including all permanent members of the Security Council.

Therefore, a concrete solution to prevent Russia from imposing its decisions at UN level cannot be adopted at present, perhaps only if the Charter were to be repealed in its entirety and replaced by another nominative act, which would provide that decisions would be taken only in the General Assembly.

With the replacement of the Charter, the new normative act should no longer provide for the exercise of the veto, and a provision should be inserted in its content expressly regulating the prohibition, for States which are parties to a dispute triggered by them, not to be able to exercise their right to vote under any circumstances.

At the same time, in order to create equality between states in the adoption of decisions, one of the amendments should also aim to remove the distinction between permanent and non-permanent members, thus achieving a complete reform of the Security Council by removing its monopoly, in which case the General Assembly resolutions should become legally binding, no longer limited to mere recommendations.

Moreover, the admission of states to the UN should no longer be based on criteria relating to their military capabilities for the maintenance of international peace and security, as this is one of the criteria that are being analyzed for NATO membership. It should be borne in mind that the role of the UN is to carry out peacekeeping and peace restoration or post-conflict rehabilitation operations.

Although the UN can authorize through the Security Council under Article 42 of the Charter the use of military force to settle a dispute, the organization does not have the military capabilities to be considered an admission criterion for member states, as the armed forces belong to NATO member states.

As regards Romania's position on Security Council reform, our country supported the increase in the number of members in the Council and the granting of an additional non-permanent seat to the Eastern European Group.

Romania also supported the proposal for Germany and Japan to become permanent members of the Council, as well as the African, Asian and Latin American countries' efforts to be better represented in the Council.

Conclusions

Unlike the General Assembly, the Security Council was designed to be an operational body, adopting coercive measures that may involve the use of armed force through its five permanent members. However, its competence to conduct military operations under the aegis of the UN is limited to those to maintain or restore international peace and security.

However, its peacekeeping operations have allowed it to intervene in a non-coercive way in areas such as good governance, humanitarian law and the reconstruction of crisis-affected states.

The lack of agreement among the permanent members on political decisions or military intervention has led the UN, and hence the Council, to refocus its attention on peace operations.

In view of the existing difficulties in revising the Charter, an interim solution, which could be applied in the future to avoid the excessive use of the veto and to reform the Council, could be to share decision-making competences between the Council and the General Assembly on political issues, as a body with all UN member states as representatives, so that each state can express its views on international security issues, thus aiming at a definitive abolition of the veto.

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